

LEARNING INFLUENCES AFFECTING THE PROFICIENCY IN SOLVING WORD PROBLEMS IN MATHEMATICS AMONG GRADE 8 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Problem solving skill of students is one of the most important factors to achieve proficiency in mathematics. In this regard, there are learning influences that should be taken into account and be addressed to provide intellectual practices to know its effect to the proficiency in solving word problems in mathematics of the students. This study on learning influences affecting the proficiency in solving word problems in mathematics aimed to determine the perceptions on learning influences in terms of cognitive and affective areas and their relationship to problem solving skill of students. The use of a survey questionnaire and learning activity sheet with scoring rubric and a descriptive correlational design led in achieving the objectives of the study participated by 150 Grade 8 students of San Pablo City Integrated High School of the academic year 2020 – 2021. The mean and standard deviation was utilized to determine the perceptions of students on learning influences. Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between students' perceptions on learning influences and their proficiency in solving word problems. The result of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between cognitive learning influence identified as coping strategies and the problem-solving ability as to resources, heuristics, control, and belief systems. Furthermore, the result also showed that there is a significant relationship between affective learning influence as to self-esteem and the problem-solving ability as to belief systems. On the other hand, rest of learning influences as to managing behavior, conscious control, attitude, self – efficacy and achievement motive showed no significant relationship with the problem-solving ability in terms of resources, heuristics, control, and belief systems. The study suggests the practice of students to write feedbacks and responses to every learning activity sheet on problem solving that will help them improve their problem-solving skill in mathematics.

Keywords: Problem Solving Skill, Learning Influences, Proficiency, Word Problems, Problem Solving Ability.